

SUPERSHINE

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

Authors: Alice De Ferrari (ICONS), Jardel Sestrem (ICONS)

Technical references

Project Acronym	SUPERSHINE
Project Title	S=Smart U=Upgraded asset-values and quality of life P=Public Private Partnership E=Extended Energy Efficiency R=Renewables triggered by the project SH=Social Housing I=Investment N=Net Zero E=European
Project Duration	November 2022– March 2026
Deliverable No.	D6.1
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Work Package	WP6 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Task	T6.1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy
Lead beneficiary	ICONS
Authors	Alice De Ferrari, Jardel Sestrem
Reviewer(s)	Paola Zerilli (UoY)
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2023

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

v	Date	Beneficiaries	Trach changes
1.0	22/09/2023	ICONS	Consolidated draft
1.1	25/09/2023	APRE	Minor corrections and formatting
1.2	26/09/2023	UoY	Review by UoY
2.0	29/09/2023	APRE	Final Review

Table of contents

Technical references	2
Table of contents	3
1. Executive summary.....	5
2. Introduction: an integrated approach to Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication	6
2.1. Relation with SUPER-i project	7
2.2. Objectives and the SUPERSHINE approach to dissemination, communication, and exploitation.....	7
2.3. Obligation and right to use the EU Emblem.....	8
3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication	10
3.1. Preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identification and exploitation pathways .	10
3.2. Target audiences & key stakeholders.....	12
3.2.1. Policymakers and public authorities.....	13
3.2.2. Social housing organisations.....	14
3.2.3. Financing institutions	14
3.2.4. Construction and building industry.....	15
3.2.5. Technology services and products.....	15
3.2.6. Residents.....	16
3.2.7. Scientific community.....	16
3.2.8. Civil society actors, NGOs	16
3.2.9. Media	16
3.3. Key messages	16
3.4. A tailored approach to Dissemination and Communication	18
3.5. Dissemination & Communication channels	19
3.5.1. Website	19
3.5.2. Social networks and social media strategy	20
3.5.3. Media multipliers	22
3.6. Dissemination & Communication materials and formats.....	22
3.6.1. Formats	22
3.6.2. Editorial content	25
3.7. Clustering, synergies, and events.....	27
3.8. Management of communication, dissemination, and exploitation	27
3.8.1. Responsibility in the consortium	27
3.9. Monitoring.....	29
3.9.1. ICONS’s monitoring process.....	29
3.9.2. ICONS’s engagement indexes: CEI encompassing - PEI, SEI, WEI.....	29
3.10. The projects’ visual identity	30
4. Exploitation strategy.....	32
4.1. Replication and upscaling	32
4.2. Sustainability plan of the SUPERSHINE portal.....	33

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

4.3. Product/service development based on knowledge generated	33
4.4. Upscaling of technology TRLs and commercialisation	34
4.5. Academic and research exploitation	34
5. Conclusions.....	35
References.....	36

Executive summary

This Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan sets out the strategy to effectively promote and exploit SUPERSHINE's results. It defines the processes and activities to be implemented and guides stakeholders towards the maximization of the project's impact.

The plan provides an overall framework integrating communication, dissemination, and exploitations activities. It starts from the definition of the overall Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and preliminary mapping of the main stakeholder groups. It goes on with the formulation of targeted key messages and the identification of the most suitable dissemination tools and channels, outlining a timeline and envisioning proper dissemination pathways. Additionally, the plan includes monitoring activities to ensure the maximization of content outreach and engagement, thus assessing the project's impact on target audiences. The document ends with a preliminary outline of the main exploitation strategies envisioned for the different project's results after the project's end.

The content of this document follows the following structure:

- **Chapter 3** explains SUPERSHINE's integrated approach to communication, dissemination, and exploitation, summarising the project's key objectives.
- **Chapter 4** focuses on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Starting with the preliminary identification of SUPERSHINE's overall Key Exploitable Results (KERs), it envisions possible exploitations pathways and identifies the main stakeholder groups who can help maximize the project's impact. Afterwards, it articulates the key messages and identifies the communication channels and formats that will be used to spread information linked to the project and promote its results. Subsequently, the chapter describes the integrated way all the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities will be managed, highlighting the responsibilities' distribution within the consortium. In the end, the monitoring processes and methodology developed by ICONS are described with reference to the dissemination and communication activities' impacts along with the indicators that will be used to evaluate the audience's engagement with the communication materials.
- **Chapter 5** is about SUPERSHINE's exploitation strategy and implements an impact-driven approach to ensure the uptake and sustainability of the project's results.
- **Chapter 4** sums up the previous chapter and draws some preliminary conclusions.

This plan is a "living" document, which will be updated during the project's implementation at in D6.2 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part2 (M29). New approaches and methods will be suggested based on regular reviews and evaluations of KPIs and engagement rates.

Introduction: an integrated approach to Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication

SUPERSHINE focuses on renovating social housing to alleviate energy poverty by assisting households struggling with energy bills.

To reach this goal it is fundamental to develop and manage an effective and efficient communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy. Dissemination (D), Exploitation (E) and Communication (C) activities will be highly integrated and rolled out in synergy with each other to:

- raise visibility on the project and inform target groups and broader communities on the benefits and impacts of the project (C);
- share knowledge and engage the key players, key enablers and early-adopters involved with a dedicated and customised strategy (D);
- set the pathway to the exploitation and sustainability of the SUPERSHINE results (E).

The impact-oriented and holistic approach of the SUPERSHINE “Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results” (PDCE) will be aimed at generating impacts through i) awareness and understanding; ii) acceptance of innovative approaches; iii) uptake and upscale of the project’s results beyond the end of the project.

More specifically, the PDCE is propped up on the mapping of stakeholders, the analysis of their needs and, accordingly, the definition of their role and level of involvement with the project’s results. This methodology allows us to design targeted and direct actions (messages, contents, channels, tools, engagement activities) at different geographical levels over time. Additionally, it supports the elaboration of exploitation strategies to further leverage project’s results after its end. Stakeholder groups are already identified in this report, the analysis will be consolidated in D6.3 Library of Key Exploitable Results and Stakeholder Mapping, and fully integrated in D6.2 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part2 (M29).

The impacts and effectiveness of the strategy will be continuously monitored and measured through a proprietary methodology developed by ICONS based on a set of indicators and indexes, among them the Community Engagement - Index-CEI; the CEI measures the actual stakeholders’ engagement with the project. Monitoring activities will provide continuous feeds to the PDEC to optimize and upgrade it along the different project phases.

With regards to the exploitation process, the approach adopted will be comprehensive in scope, and cover all types of results (commercial and non-commercial) and every possible exploitation pathway. This will be achieved through a three-step approach:

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

- Identification of all Key Exploitable Results (KERs): SUPERSHINE will produce several KERs, which will be compiled in the Library of Key Exploitable Results (D6.3). KERs will be reviewed and updated during the project implementation.
- IPR assessment and analysis of exploitation options: IP ownership and applicable IPRs will be assessed, and partners' exploitation intentions and detailed strategies will be elaborated.
- Design of a plan with partners' joint and individual strategies for accelerating replication.

The overall goal is to pave the way for the exploitation of both individual and joint results and ensure their sustainability. The strategies will be constantly refined during the course of the project. The initial strategies will be available in D6.3 Library of Key Exploitable Results and Stakeholder Mapping, updated in D6.2 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part2 (M29) and will be finalised in D6.5 Exploitation plan (M41). It is expected that through the implementation of an effective dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, the stakeholders will support and adopt SUPERSHINE results, going beyond the project lifetime.

Relation with SUPER-i project

The SUPERSHINE project originated from the knowledge gained through the SUPER-i project (Horizon 2020 - grant agreement No.101028220). Both projects share the same consortium, a well-established network, and a community in the process of forming. As a result, it was deemed essential to maintain a robust connection in communication, dissemination and exploitation, to maximize the benefits of everyone's contributions.

Regarding the integration of communication activities between the two projects, particularly concerning the website and social media channels, a cohesive approach will be implemented. This approach aims to ensure seamless coordination and optimization of communication efforts for both SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE projects.

Objectives and the SUPERSHINE approach to dissemination, communication, and exploitation

SUPERSHINE Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation (CDE) strategy is built following an impact-oriented and integrated approach to reach, engage and synergize key target audiences and stakeholders. The aim is to maximise the potential short-term outcomes and long-term impacts of the project and the wide-scale roll-out of its KERs. The strategy revolves around three major phases:

- **Phase I:** Raise awareness and interest among stakeholders at large about energy poverty and replicable models of smart districts, based on energy efficiency, affordability, and sustainability and ensure adequate and well-targeted funding. It's relevant at this stage to build and maintain a common project identity. It will help to increase engagement and awareness of the project's expected results and impacts.
- **Phase II: Increase engagement to generate interest and acceptance.** SUPERSHINE will focus on disseminating the identified KERs and engaging with the general audience and key targets to demonstrate the benefits of the project innovation. This outreach of contents will be particularly supportive of Energy Efficiency (EE) renovations of social housing, co-designed solutions, and innovative financial solutions such as Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) and Green Public Procurement (GPP).

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

- **Phase III: Foster uptake, upscale and replication of results.** A targeted engagement strategy will be implemented in line with the mapping of the stakeholders, by defining their role and level of involvement with KERs and value proposition analysis. Targeted and direct actions (messages, contents, channels, tools, engagement activities) will be designed and will act as key drivers for exploitation. Indeed, this strategy will create the preconditions to stimulate broader replication of KERs and engage with new communities and wider audiences. These would facilitate the uptake of KERs and ensure continuous dissemination, exploitation and replication after the project's end.

A local dissemination and promotion plan will be developed at district level in collaboration with local partner in Trieste (Italy), Herning (Denmark) and Riga (Latvia), to fuel local dissemination and transferability of project knowledge and results.

The impacts and effectiveness of the strategy will be continuously monitored and measured through a set of indicators and indexes, among them the Community Engagement Index-CEI by ICONS measuring the actual stakeholders' engagement with the project. Monitoring activities will provide continuous feeds to the Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and impact analysis, to optimize and upgrade it along the different project phases.

Obligation and right to use the EU Emblem

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, any communication and dissemination activity of the beneficiaries related to the action must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Any dissemination of results or outputs must also indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

For more information, partners can refer to the article 17 of the Grant Agreement.

Download:

The EU emblem:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

Guidelines on the use of the EU emblem:

https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-05/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

Furthermore, as the project receives co-funding from UKRI, the UK's national innovation agency, the "UKRI Innovate UK" logo is also displayed as acknowledgment on any communication and dissemination activity relating to the project, besides the EU emblem.

Co-Funded by

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

Preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identification and exploitation pathways

The main goal of SUPERSHINE is to assist the renovation of social housing and contribute to decrease energy poverty. The project will tackle community involvement and drive new business models and funding methods in collaboration with industry partners to facilitate comprehensive and integrated renovation interventions and technologies. The SUPERSHINE lighthouse districts will be characterised by energy-efficient buildings supported by responsive technologies that optimise resources while promoting well-being and sustainable lifestyles. Thus, the project is anticipated to produce relevant results that can be capitalized by partners to create long-lasting positive impact in the social housing sector.

According to the EC, results are defined as *“any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as models, tools, data, knowledge, or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights”*. The focus of the exploitation process is on the Key Exploitable Results, which encompass the main project outcomes that may be used by the project partners or other relevant stakeholders outside the project. KERs can be either commercially exploited for the delivery of products or services, or lay the foundation for further research, work, or innovations.

To ensure an effective exploitation of the project’s results, SUPERSHINE exploitation approach will be comprehensive in scope, covering all types of results and exploitation routes. KERs will be identified and monitored in parallel with the project’s progress and achievements. For each KER, exploitation strategies will be elaborated to ensure the use of results by the consortium partners, as well as their uptake by stakeholders (e.g., researchers, entrepreneurs, policy makers, investors, etc.)

KERs can be individual or joint, whether they were generated by a single partner or jointly developed by two or more partners. Individual results are developed by a single partner and individually exploited by the single owner outside the project (e.g., a new model or methodology developed by a single partner; specific expertise or knowledge gained). Joint results represent the main assets of the project, usually co-developed by several partners, and for which specific arrangements among owners should be put in place for future exploitation.

The exploitation process in SUPERSHINE will be deployed through a three-step approach:

1. Identification and continuous monitoring of all KERs and key stakeholders
2. Assessment of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)
3. Elaboration of partners’ joint and individual exploitation plans

The identification of KERs is the first step of the exploitation process and lays the basis for the elaboration of the final exploitation plan towards the end of the project. This step involves a comprehensive mapping of the

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

project’s expected results to be presented in a dedicated database “D6.3 Library of Key Exploitable Results and Stakeholder Mapping”.

The library of exploitable results consists of a document that compiles all KERs generated in the project and includes key information such as intellectual property (IP) ownership, IPR measures, partners' initial exploitation intentions, and more. The library is developed in collaboration with project partners and will serve as a foundation for drafting the exploitation strategies. Furthermore, D6.3 will anticipate an initial stakeholder mapping focused on the key target groups for the uptake of results, as well as potential partners (either research, commercial, or policy) that can support the exploitation of KERs.

The exploitation plans will identify possible, and most appropriate exploitation routes for the KERs, corresponding to the nature of the different results, and the organizations involved. It will highlight the results value proposition and describe the concrete exploitation measures and steps to ensure that results meet real needs to be taken up. Additionally, the Intellectual Property rights (IPR) will be assessed to avoid any issues that may hinder the exploitation of results.

The table below provides an initial list of expected KERs. It will be reviewed and updated during the implementation of the project according to the project’s developments. Additionally, KERs will be published on the Horizon Results Platform with different levels of detail, depending on their confidentiality.

Table 1 SUPERSHINE preliminary Key Exploitable Results

KER	Type	IP Ownership	IPR
Blueprint business and financial models and evaluation methodology	Models and data, including also, financial mechanisms	UoY, WP3 and WP5 contributing partners	Copyright in publications
Blueprint SLCA, LCA and LCC models	Models and data	CIRCE, UoY, WP3 and WP5 contributing partners	Copyright in publications
Blueprint social acceptance and co-design models	Models, including both strategy and KPIs	ICONS, APRE, WP1, WP3 and WP5 contributing partners	Copyright in publications
Blueprint technologies	Technologies	CIRCE, Tech owners in WP4	Copyright in publications
SUPERHINE portal	Technology	EEIP, WP2 contributing partners	Copyright

Results described in Table 1 are related to models and technologies, with a key focus on the SUPERHINE portal as the platform enabling replication of results and serving as an exploitation channel for the other individual and joint results. During the project execution, other results will be identified, analysed, and their exploitation potential will be evaluated to determine whether they qualify as KERs.

A summary description of all KERs is provided here:

- **Blueprint business and financial models and evaluation methodology:** this result comprises innovative bottom-up business models and financial instruments to help promote energy efficiency,

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

circularity, improvements for social housing tenants and providers. A special focus is given to Public Private Partnerships and Green Public Procurement.

- **Blueprint SLCA, LCA and LCC models:** LCA (Life Cycle Assessment), SLCA (Social Life Cycle Assessment), and LCC (Life Cycle Costing) are tools used to evaluate various aspects of solutions implemented in the lighthouse districts, primary focused on environmental, social, and economic aspects, respectively. The results of these analysis will support stakeholders in making informed decisions, and guide solution design, process optimization, and understanding economic viability and long-term cost implications. As such, they will be instrumental for the exploitation of KERs, and replication.
- **Blueprint social acceptance and co-design models:** this result consists of tailored social engagement models to empower and engage residents, foster co-design, co-development, and co-implementation of renovations. It further includes dedicated KPIs to measure the social acceptance of solutions implemented in the demonstration sites.
- **Blueprint technologies:** comprises detailed proofs-of-concept for the SUPERSHINE solutions tested in the lighthouse districts. Packages of innovative energy efficient technologies will be deployed to effectively defeat energy poverty.

SUPERSHINE portal: The SUPERSHINE Portal is a digital platform that will collect all data generated in the project, host the SUPERSHINE training toolkit, and the SUPERSHINE One Stop Shop. It aims to become the European reference point and hub for enterprises, stakeholders, and institutional and private investors.

Target audiences & key stakeholders

The results and activities of the SUPERSHINE project are of interest to a variety of stakeholder groups, including social housing managers and local authorities, who can promote an innovative low carbon revamping of social housing districts, investors, as key partners in this renovation process, as well as industrial players who provide services and products that underpin such renovations.

Therefore, a comprehensive mapping of stakeholders is important to effectively carry out dissemination and exploitation activities. Indeed, identifying stakeholders and understanding their specific needs and interests enables the development of targeted dissemination activities and messages, reach, and involve relevant external parties in the execution of the project and in the exploitation of project results, hence maximizing its impact.

The stakeholder mapping is not intended as an exhaustive list, but rather as a framework of reference that will inform the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy execution and provide guidance on the potential targets, partners, channels, and enablers. This chapter provides a preliminary mapping of stakeholders which will be updated throughout the project's duration.

Step 1: Identifying stakeholders

Considering the definition of "stakeholders" provided above, the process of stakeholder's identification requires understanding which project results the project will deliver (e.g., models, tools, datasets, policy recommendations etc.), and how partners expect to exploit results. Based on the KERs already identified (see Table 1), a total of 10 stakeholder groups have been identified and are described in Table 3 below.

Table 2 SUPERSHINE stakeholder groups and stakeholders

Group	Stakeholders
Polymakers and public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European institutions and agencies • National governments, Local authorities, and bodies
Social housing organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public providers of social housing • Private providers of social housing
Financial institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local financial institutions • EU financial institutions
Construction and building industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction & Refurbishment services • Engineering companies
Technology services and products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HW/SW providers for the housing sector • Energy-efficiency technology companies
Energy companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESCOS • Utility companies
Residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tenants • Consumers • Prosumers
Associations, clusters, and membership organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Housing associations • National and regional federations
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia • Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) • Technical experts
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National and European media

Step 2: Stakeholder Profiling

This section focuses on providing a short profile for each of the stakeholder groups and sub-groups identified, including their reference market and operational context, along with their main interests SUPERSHINE’s results.

Polymakers and public authorities

EU institutions and agencies

Although the EU has no direct competence on housing policy (Scanlon, K., et al, 2014), project outputs will contribute to the achievement of key policy goals of the EU, embedded in the European Green Deal, and the EU Renovation Wave Strategy. Furthermore, the European Commission (EC) supports initiatives tackling the topic of housing deprivation and energy efficiency and provides funding for energy retrofit projects through

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

several avenues, including the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and Cohesion Funds (Rohrer, L., & Lidmo, J. (2022).

National governments, Local authorities and bodies

In many EU countries, there is a trend to more social housing decision-making from the national to the local levels of governance (Hesterberg, C. Stiffler, M., 2015). While there might be overarching national housing policies set by central governments, the implementation and customization of these policies often occur at the local level, as housing needs can vary significantly from one locality to another. Besides being key providers and investors in social housing, national, regional, and municipal policymakers can influence financing arrangements, defining principles for business and management models of social housing, among many other things. Therefore, SUPERSHINE project outputs can not only inform policymaking, but also support the strategic replication of successful solutions demonstrated in the project.

Social housing organisations

In EU countries, both public and private entities play roles in providing social housing. Social housing organizations are the final users of the key results of the projects (i.e., novel business and financial models, blueprint technologies), and therefore, consists of key stakeholders of the project. They can be divided between public and private social housing providers.

Public social housing providers

Public social housing providers are typically government-owned or government-controlled entities responsible for offering affordable housing options to individuals and families. These providers are often operated by local or regional authorities (usually by municipalities, either directly or through dedicated publicly owned companies) (Pittini, A., Laino, E., 2011). Some examples include *Wiener Wohnen*, Vienna's public housing company and one of the largest municipal housing providers in Europe¹, and Vestia, formally Stichting Vestia, the largest public housing corporation in the Netherlands.

Private social housing providers

Public providers co-exist with a growing private sector, mainly consisting of non-profit organizations, cooperatives, and a smaller portion of private for-profit companies. These providers often receive support from government subsidies, grants, or favourable financing to maintain affordability for their tenants (Pittini, A., Laino, E., 2011). Commonly, public providers manage the existing social housing stock in countries, while the private sector is responsible for developing new social housing (IZA, 2013), and the specific roles and proportions of these providers can vary significantly from one EU member state to another (Pittini, A., Laino, E., 2011). Some examples of private providers of affordable housing include Vesteda and Bouwinvest, in the Netherlands.

Financial institutions

Local financial institutions and EU financial institutions

Financial institutions play a crucial role in the development, maintenance, and improvement of social housing infrastructure. Indeed, sustainable, and affordable finance is one key pillar to support the provision of affordable housing in the long-term. During the past decades, social housing has experienced an increasing diversification of its finance mechanisms and sources (IZA, 2013), and it has become common for social housing providers to borrow from commercial financial institutions. Financial resources can also be obtained

¹ Available at: <https://socialhousing.wien/organizations/city-of-vienna-wiener-wohnen>

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

through loans from various banks and special financial institutions, including the European Investment bank. The innovative bottom-up financial solutions implemented in the project will be informative for commercial financial institutions looking to provide well-targeted funding for the social housing sector.

Construction and building industry

Construction & Refurbishment services

Construction and refurbishment companies are responsible for the physical construction and renovation work, including installation of energy efficient building envelopes (insulation, windows, roofing, etc.). These companies often offer construction services, comprising the full range of building and refurbishment activities, handling interior components, flooring, walls, ceilings, etc. These local industries will also be the main users of the SUPERSHINE "One-stop-shop" solution, which will offer a complete renovation package for social housing residents and managers. Therefore, local players can leverage this innovative offering to enhance their service portfolio, providing clients with a convenient and reliable option for their renovation needs.

Engineering and architectural firms

Engineering companies support developers, home builders, government and municipal authorities, and property managers to deliver successful and profitable residential developments and their associated infrastructure. Engineering companies provide multi-disciplinary expertise in areas of residential planning, design, and construction, including building engineering, city planning, etc. Similarly, these companies can benefit from the SUPERSHINE "One-stop-shop" solution.

Technology services and products

HW/SW providers for the housing sector

This group of companies comprises suppliers of cutting-edge technologies and products with a primary focus on enhancing energy efficiency. These are HW/SW companies and other SMEs providing innovative services. Their offerings encompass a wide range of solutions designed to optimize energy usage and reduce environmental impact. Some examples of products and technologies provided by these companies include lighting solutions, smart building controls, renewable energy systems, energy monitoring and management tools, and more.

Energy-efficiency technology companies

The Energy Efficiency Tech sector comprises innovative SMEs and startups. These companies offer technological solutions and services for the measurement, management, and control of energy consumption and associated costs. They focus on equipment, products, or solutions designed to deliver energy savings and to reduce energy consumption. The home energy management systems market has several major players including companies like Honeywell International Inc., The General Electric Company, among others. Additionally, a growing number of innovative SMEs is focused on applying predictive and proactive IoT-based building automation systems.

Energy companies

Energy companies are involved in the sustainable social housing landscape by contributing their expertise, technologies, and resources to enhance energy efficiency and environmental sustainability. Their involvement can encompass energy audits and assessments, renewable energy integration, smart energy management, among other aspects of the renovation process. ESCOS, for instance, can collaborate with social housing managers and owners in implementing EE renovation.

Residents

Citizens and residents are pivotal stakeholders in housing renovation projects, particularly in the context of social housing. As the final consumers and beneficiaries of these interventions, their perspectives, needs, and experiences are of key importance. This stakeholder group consists of individuals and families who live in the housing units undergoing renovation. Social housing residents contribute to the long-term sustainability, besides providing valuable data and other relevant inputs for the execution and evaluation of the solutions. Furthermore, residents of social housing can be final-end users and decision markers to what concerns the adoption of the solutions. Residents of social housing include tenants, consumers but also prosumers (those directly involved in collective renewable energy production and consumption).

Scientific community

Universities and research institutes dedicated to studying and educating about energy poverty and energy refurbishment will also leverage the outcomes of the SUPERSHINE project, by advancing and building upon the knowledge that will be made available in open access publications.

Civil society actors, NGOs

Civil society organizations, including Housing Europe and various national and regional federations of social housing, play a key role in advocating for the fundamental right to accessible and reasonably priced housing. These organizations are committed to supporting the transition toward eco-friendly and sustainable residences. As a result, they not only serve as crucial avenues for engaging with social housing providers but also hold significance as key players within the broader political landscape of the European Union. Housing Europe, the European Federation of Public, Cooperative and Social Housing providers, for instance, counts on a network of 43 national and regional federations in 31 countries.

Media

Media actors will be key informants and multipliers of the project outputs. Communication activities will be key to each of the goals of the project, and support dissemination and Exploitation of results. This includes local, national, and European news outlets.

Key messages

Several target-oriented key messages have been designed to guarantee the consistency in communicating the SUPERSHINE main goals. Key messages are a crucial mean to provide meaningful impacts and expected outputs to the audience.

The identified stakeholders and the related key messages are listed in the following table. These can be further declined into powerful statements.

Table 3 - SUPERSHINE Key messages

Key message	Key words	Targeted stakeholders
-------------	-----------	-----------------------

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

<p>SUPERSHINE is leading the way on the journey towards zero-carbon living. Our commitment to sustainable practices, energy efficiency, and affordability is transforming the housing landscape, one neighbourhood at a time. Join us as we pioneer a new era of responsible living.</p>	<p>Zero-carbon living Energy efficiency</p>	<p>Social housing organisations Tech providers ESCOs Energy companies</p>
<p>SUPERSHINE is a new EU project aiming at transforming social housing to combat energy poverty. Our focus: energy efficiency, affordability, and sustainability. We're creating replicable smart districts, ensuring ample funding, and pioneering Europe's shift to zero-carbon living.</p>	<p>Energy efficiency Energy poverty Smart district Urban transition</p>	<p>Construction and building industry</p>
<p>Collaboration is the cornerstone of our approach at SUPERSHINE. We're uniting diverse stakeholders, from local communities to industry leaders, in a concerted effort to tackle the pressing challenges of energy poverty and environmental sustainability. Together, we're forging a path toward a more sustainable and resilient future</p>	<p>Energy efficiency Energy poverty Social impact Consortium of excellence</p>	<p>Policy makers Local government</p>
<p>SUPERSHINE's approach encompasses incentivizing, funding, promoting sustainability in construction, and decarbonizing heating and cooling, igniting large-scale renovations, fostering cross-sector partnerships, unleashing innovative technologies, nurturing human-centric housing models, and building a network of social housing providers for a sustainable tomorrow.</p>	<p>Financial schemes, roadmaps specific solutions</p>	<p>Financial institutions Construction and building industry</p>
<p>With SUPERSHINE, we're reshaping housing for a sustainable tomorrow. Our initiatives don't just stop at renovating buildings; we're redefining the way communities engage with their environments and each other. Together, we're creating a blueprint for a more sustainable, inclusive, and vibrant future in Europe.</p>	<p>Energy efficiency Energy poverty</p>	<p>Policy makers Local government Financial institutions General Public</p>
<p>SUPERSHINE project will assist and support the European Commission to implement the European Green Deal.</p>	<p>European commission, European Green Deal</p>	<p>Local government Policy makers General public</p>
<p>Our vision at SUPERSHINE is to light up the path to a brighter and more sustainable future by championing energy-efficient living. We believe that every household deserves affordable and eco-friendly housing, and we're making that vision a reality through innovative projects and initiatives.</p>	<p>Energy efficiency Energy poverty Social impact</p>	<p>Social housing organisations Tech providers ESCOs Energy companies</p>

A tailored approach to Dissemination and Communication

The following table shows how each category identified through the stakeholder mapping exercise will be addressed by the project dissemination and communication activities. Depending on stakeholders' needs, dissemination content will be tailored and relayed through formats and channels considered the most effective and impactful.

Table 4 Target Group & C&D Dissemination Formats & C&D Channels

Target group	D&C Formats	D&C Channels
Social housing organizations	Flyer Press releases Videos Policy Brief Info-packs Best Practice Handbook	Website Social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) Events, conferences and workshops Media multipliers E-newsletters
Construction and building industry	Flyer Press releases Videos Info-packs Best Practice Handbook	Website Social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) Events, conferences, workshops Media multipliers
Financial institutions	Videos Journalistic articles Flyer Info-packs Policy Brief Best Practice Handbook	Website Events, conferences, workshops E-newsletters Media multipliers
Technology services and products	Flyer Press releases Videos Info-packs Best Practice Handbook	Website Social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) Events, conferences, workshops Media multipliers Scientific journals
Scientific and technical community	Flyer Press and news releases Scientific publications Info-packs Videos	Events, conferences, workshops Clustering activities Website Social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) Media multipliers Scientific journals E-newsletters
Policy makers	Flyer Policy Brief Info-packs News and press releases Journalistic articles Sector events Webinars Videos Video-interviews Best Practice Handbook	Website Social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) Events and conferences Media multipliers Sister project's websites
General public	Flyer	Website

	Press releases Journalistic articles Videos News releases	Social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) Media multipliers
Media	Press and news releases Journalistic articles Best Practice Handbook	Media Multipliers

Dissemination & Communication channels

The dissemination and communication activities that ICONS will carry out during the course of the project involve a number of channels, summarised in the table below.

Table 5 - SUPERSHINE channels

Channel	Description	Target
Website	The SUPERSHINE website acts as the main online reference for the project, providing content and materials to stakeholders and the public. It was launched in January 2022, in the framework of the SUPER-I project. It was redesigned to visually and textually showcase the coexistence of both projects prominently.	All
Social networks (Twitter, LinkedIn)	The project envisages a strong involvement of SUPERSHINE community through its social channels. Also in this case, the channels are in common with the SUPER-I project.	All
Media multipliers	These are external platforms that republish the journalistic articles, news and press releases written by SUPERSHINE.	Social housing organisations, Construction and building industry, Financial institutions, Technology services and products, Scientific community

Website

The website is a reference for all the subjects involved in the project as well as an entry point to SUPERSHINE addressing different target audiences: social housing organizations, the construction and building industry, financial institutions, technology providers, the scientific community and the public.

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

With the objective of recognizing the strong interconnection between SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE, a collaborative decision was made in agreement with both project consortia to combine efforts and enhance the existing work by sharing the website.

Consequently, the SUPER-i website will undergo restructuring to incorporate information related to the SUPERSHINE project. Certain sections of the site will be shared to improve user readability and maximize overall visibility.

The new website structure will include common sections for news, events, and resources. To distinguish whether specific content belongs to either project, a system of labels will be implemented. This labelling system will help differentiate between news, events, and deliverables associated with each respective project.

The homepage will be redesigned to visually and textually showcase the coexistence of both projects prominently. This will ensure that visitors can readily understand the collaboration between SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE.

Additionally, to foster effective communication, the Newsletter will be shared, allowing stakeholders to stay informed about updates and progress from both projects in a unified manner.

Figure 1 - SUPER -i and SUPERSHINE website homepage

The website is a living tool in continuous evolution as it will be regularly updated in terms of contents, new graphic layouts, tools, and features, according to the needs of the project. During the project, regular updates will mainly concern the "News" and "Events" pages. These updates will come in the form of posts created by ICONS with support from project partners. Efforts will be made to keep texts simple, and yet scientifically accurate and thus understandable by a broad audience.

The website is accessible to all viewers with no restrictions due to its inclusive design. It removes bias and assumptions from the website so that users do not feel excluded due to an impairment, demographics, or other circumstances. For instance, colours and typography that make up the project's visual identity and inform the web design were selected to remove any barrier to accessing it.

The project website also works as an online virtual space containing all institutional information, including reports and deliverables. ICONS will manage hosting of the website until 4 years after the project ends.

Social networks and social media strategy

The SUPERSHINE project will be promoted through its social media channels to gain visibility and spread its objectives and its results. Given the wide accessibility that these channels offer, each SUPERSHINE profile will

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

work as the main interface with whom the broad public will interact with, for example by sharing their contents and participating to a campaign.

ICONS has implemented an accurate social media strategy, considering the diverse audience involved, which may vary depending on the social media platforms used and the most effective way to communicate the SUPERSHINE project.

With the same approach used for the website, it was decided to also share the social accounts with the SUPER-i project. Since December 2022, the accounts have been renamed in SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE projects, and the aim is to build a community interested in the issues addressed by both projects.

Figure 2 - First tweet announcing the merge of the SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE channel

As of July 2023, the Twitter channel has 434 followers while the LinkedIn page has 158 followers.

SUPERSHINE will produce regular posts on both social networks. The purpose is to keep online communities interested and informed about the project, its progress and activities, and upcoming events. This will enable our project to establish relationships with groups and LinkedIn pages grounded on the social housing ecosystem, the tech providers and other targets.

The members of the consortium are encouraged to follow existing LinkedIn groups on a regular basis and post news (produced by the project) and facts worth bringing to the attention of these groups. It should be noted that the partners will carefully choose these LinkedIn groups having in mind the SUPERSHINE stakeholders' audience. Consortium members are also encouraged to share project news with their networks, aiming at increasing outreach. In the long run, they may hopefully become multipliers of the project's dissemination strategy. To support this process, the project will produce an editorial plan made up of regular posts to get the public's attention regarding SUPERSHINE main results: public deliverables, scientific publications, details and follow-up news about the progress made by the project, and facts worth bringing up to attract the targeted online community's attention.

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

With the aim of monitoring the impact of conversations about the project that extend beyond those directly managed by ICONS, the consortium has also established an official hashtag for the project: #SUPERSHINE_eu (a SUPER-i related hashtag was created too). ICONS and the whole consortium will use this hashtag to track posts related to SUPERSHINE and collect both quantitative and qualitative data regarding its impact.

Media multipliers

External media multipliers will be used to disseminate contents of general interest produced by SUPERSHINE.

These multipliers are external platforms that have syndication agreements with ICONS. The most used multipliers are EU Agenda, AlphaGalileo and Phys.org. Additional channels with a focus on the topics covered by SUPERSHINE will also be included in the project distribution list. Products to be distributed will include journalistic articles, video interviews, press and news releases on SUPERSHINE.

The rest of the SUPERSHINE consortium is encouraged to republish the project's press and news releases via their own networks. For monitoring purposes, they will have to inform ICONS once they re-distribute the above-mentioned materials.

ICONS will regularly monitor all communication materials produced by the project to quantify their outreach and understand the interaction and level of engagement generated by project's news, press releases and journalistic articles.

Dissemination & Communication materials and formats

Formats

Within SUPERSHINE, ICONS will oversee the production of content-specific DC formats and will take care of their distribution through dedicated channels, thus maximising impact in terms of awareness, acceptance, and uptake. The following materials and formats will be developed:

Table 6 - Formats and targets

Material/Format	Description	Target
Communication kit	The SUPERSHINE communication kit will entail a leaflet, and a presentation video. Communication materials will be distributed both online (as downloadable materials on the website), and offline (to be displayed at workshops, exhibitions and external events attended by the partners). The materials' design will be consistent with the project's visual identity.	All
Technical factsheets/ Infopacks	They will feature various technical insights and results from the project. Each will cover specific content and will be distributed to key stakeholders and published on the online platform.	Tech Providers Construction Sector Social Housing Org

Policy brief	Policy briefs can be a highly effective formats for disseminating technical information and influencing policy decisions.	Policy Makers
Best Practice Handbook	A comprehensive guide that provides expert insights, proven methods, and practical guidelines regarding the project outcomes. It aims to offer optimal approaches and strategies to implement the project results in the future.	Tech Providers Construction Sector Social Housing Org Policy Makers
Scientific/technical publications	Scientific publications will present the cutting-edge results from SUPERSHINE. Scientific articles and papers will be published in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings.	Academia

Communication kit (flyer, presentation video)

The SUPERSHINE communication kit is composed by professional quality material necessary to promote the project, in line with its visual identity and key messages.

Specifically, it will include a leaflet and a project videos (presentation video). The aim of this material is to provide up-to-date information, to sustain the diffusion of results to the broad public, and to communicate in an easy and understandable way the project’s objectives, challenges and benefits to a wide range audience.

Resources from the communication kit will support project communication by allowing SUPERSHINE partners to use them as a hook to engage with stakeholders, particularly when participating in events. It will contain all the information stakeholders need to know regarding the project. All visual materials will be available in digital format for downloading.

Accountability	ICONS will oversee the development and the design of materials. WP leaders will revise texts and provide feedback. All partners will provide further information that may be necessary for the development of the kit.
-----------------------	--

Technical factsheets/Info-packs

Factsheets come in the form of fact- and info- sheets or synthetic reports. These are specifically designed for the professional community to learn about technical insights, solutions and measures developed by the project.

They allow the ICONS communication team to package technical achievements and findings into a visually attractive and easy-to-access document. The specific contents will be taken from the public deliverables and scientific publications produced by the project.

Their format makes them particularly suitable to be distributed at scientific and technical events. Moreover, they will also be made available for download from the project website and will be actively distributed to key stakeholders’ groups interested in being up to date on project results.

Accountability	ICONS will oversee the development and the graphic design of the factsheets. UoY, APRE, and other tech partners will collect content to be featured in such resources. When the content of the factsheets will be particularly technical, some partners or the coordinator will be asked to draft content, based on the guidelines provided by ICONS, who will oversee the final edits and pagination.
-----------------------	--

Final Good Practices Handbook

The SUPERSHINE Good Practices Handbook will feature the project's key achievements, best practices, lessons learned, and recommendations based on evidence gathered from the different stages of the project, from development, testing through to validation phases.

It will be issued towards the end of the project, when the SUPERSHINE partnership will be in the position to draw some conclusions from the project, worth to be shared in the scientific community.

ICONS will design the layout of the publication, while partners will provide the technical content and provide their input as to the lessons learned. It will come in electronic and printable formats.

Accountability	ICONS will work with UoY and APRE to oversee the development of the handbook. When the content is decided, ICONS will take care of the graphic design. If the content of the booklets will be particularly technical, we will ask some partners or the coordinator to draft content, based on the guidelines provided by ICONS, who will oversee the final edits and pagination.
-----------------------	--

Policy brief

A policy brief is a concise document that presents key information and recommendations on a specific policy issue or problem.

It is designed to provide policymakers, government officials, and other stakeholders with a clear and succinct overview of the issue and propose actionable policy solutions. SUPERSHINE will use policy briefs to inform decision-making of associations/initiatives representing cities and regions i.e., Covenant of Mayors, Eurocities, Committee of the Regions (CoR), Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR), the Cities Mission Board and Platforms.

SUPERSHINE will deliver 1 policy brief in the final part of the project, summarizing the final recommendations and blueprints, participation in policy discussion tables (at EU and local/regional/country level).

Accountability	UOY and BL will oversee the content of policy brief. Once approved, ICONS will design tailored formats for dissemination.
-----------------------	---

Scientific/Technical publications

The project is expected to generate scientific results worth to be disseminated in scientific conferences and published in journals.

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

SUPERSHINE papers will feature the most interesting findings sought out by the academic within the project. Possibilities to publish in open access mode will be investigated in the consortium. News about the release of SUPERSHINE scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be shared via the project website and social media channels.

Accountability	<p>Research and technical partners will be the main responsible for the release and publishing of these actions.</p> <p>APRE will keep track of all the scientific and technical publications made by SUPERSHINE scientific and technical partners within the project. Moreover, ICONS will promote such publications via the project website and social media.</p>
-----------------------	---

Editorial content

The editorial content produced by ICONS will play a distinctive role in the Communication and Dissemination activities for SUPERSHINE. A variety of formats will be considered to boost the effectiveness of the editorial activities. This multi-format approach is designed to increase and maintain effectiveness in our communication with different types of audiences.

Table 7 Editorial materials

Material/Format	Description	Target
Journalistic articles	Independent articles and interviews to project's experts and external stakeholders will be produced by professional journalists and distributed to online media, thematic portals, and other information outlets.	General public Policy makers Construction professionals Social Housing managers Tech providers Media
Press and news releases	They can be used to inform the community about the main project achievements and milestones and promote project events and progress. They will also have an information purpose and disclose information about the novelties in the field relevant for the construction sector.	General public Construction professionals Social Housing managers Tech providers SMEs and other entrepreneurs Policy makers European partnerships Associations, Clusters, and membership organisations Media
Audio-visual materials	SUPERSHINE videos will communicate the project in an easy and engaging way. Their format will be suitable for online distribution, although they may also be used to present the project at sector events.	Citizens, Policy makers; European initiatives, media

The outreach will be monitored on a regular basis thus allowing us to fine-tune the communication materials' contents, to gain more impact over time.

Journalistic articles

Independent journalistic articles and interviews will be written by professional journalists. They will cover topics linked to SUPERSHINE with an angle suitable to reach through to a wide range of audiences.

Journalistic articles aim at informing and stimulating the interest of a wider public about the topics covered by SUPERSHINE. This approach in communication is particularly effective to reach a wide range of audiences, to raise awareness and ultimately contribute to social acceptance of the project's results. The articles and interviews will be published on SUPERSHINE' website, and they will be distributed to the public at a European and at a global level using different multipliers or media platforms, namely EU Agenda, AlphaGalileo and Phys.org and other platforms which will be indicated as suitable to the project distribution. The interviews and articles will also be promoted through SUPERSHINE' social media channels.

Press and news releases

SUPERSHINE press and news releases are meant to draw the stakeholders' and the public's attention towards the project, the progress made, and the results achieved.

Press releases are particularly effective when it comes to communicating the project's main achievements and key milestones, like the release of a scientific paper or a technical deliverable.

News releases, on the other hand, have an informal structure and they use a plain language as they are easily read by the public. They are usually published on the project website to communicate news about the project, its features and its work which are all worth bringing to the attention of the SUPERSHINE community despite not being "breaking news". A news release will be produced, for example, to give explanation of an innovative concept developed by the project or on background information to a project activity.

News releases are particularly effective when informing of the participation of some members of the SUPERSHINE partnership to external events to present their latest project findings or achievement.

Both the press releases and the news releases will be published on the project website and, whenever deemed newsworthy, they'll be distributed to external online resources and news multipliers.

The members of the SUPERSHINE consortium are encouraged to actively publish and post on their own distribution channels and external media news about their project. ICONS will be watching such activity, by monitoring on a six-month basis all publications released by the partners. This exercise will be based on a dedicated template which will be circulated in the consortium twice per year.

Audio-visual materials

SUPERSHINE videos aim at communicating the project in an easy and engaging way. It can be developed in different formats (infographics and animation, scribing technique, real footage, stock images etc.) according to the audience, the targets, and the channels to be used for distribution.

To achieve optimal project outcomes and align the video productions more effectively with the SUPER-i project, the decision was made to postpone the production of the SUPERSHINE presentation video, originally planned for Month 8.

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

The video production for SUPERSHINE comprises two videos, both intended to promote awareness of the project's goals and achievements. After discussions with the APRE coordinator and the UoY scientific coordinator, it was determined that it would be more strategic to delay the video production to leverage the initial results of the project or to enhance collaboration with similar projects.

The video will be hosted on the website and will be shared on SUPERSHINE YouTube channel and other social media.

Clustering, synergies, and events

SUPERSHINE partners will participate in networking and clustering events to raise the project's visibility within the stakeholder community.

The project partners will engage and join forces with sister projects and sector partnerships. This cooperation will be made visible on the project website, where sister projects are already featured by including their name, payoff and direct URL to their projects' websites and social media channels. The SUPERSHINE newsletter will include a dedicated section where fellow projects' news and major results/ publications can be presented.

A preliminary list of sister projects and memberships is provided in the table below.

Sister projects and fellow networks	drOp ProLight SHAPE EU Social Housing Amabilina
--	--

Joint webinars and/or sessions will be organised with the sister projects to gain more visibility and reach more audiences. To support the sister projects in their joint dissemination efforts, SUPERSHINE will consider applying to the Horizon Results Booster free-of-charge service. The latter aims to identify commonalities among the members of the cluster and aims to draft a joint dissemination plan. Furthermore, to support the execution of joint dissemination activities, graphic materials, such as a video and a flyer, are produced for the cluster.

Management of communication, dissemination, and exploitation

Responsibility in the consortium

To ensure that EU-wide communication activities can reach out to the mentioned stakeholders and the general public in order to maximise the impact and the exploitation of SUPERSHINE results, full cooperation needs to be established between the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Leader (ICONS), the Scientific Coordinator (UoY) and the rest of the consortium.

There are strong interactions between the project dissemination, communication and exploitation, illustrated in the current document, and the partners' local activities, especially with stakeholders and professional audiences. Therefore, full co-operation from the rest of the team is expected. In fact, all the project partners are expected to co-operate by participating in webinars, direct interviews and

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

questionnaires to gather information necessary to define the project KERs and the most suitable exploitation strategies.

Role and responsibility of ICONS, the project coordinator and all the other member of the SUPERSHINE consortium can be summarised according to the following scheme:

Table 8. SUPERSHINE' partnership accountability in communication and dissemination

Partner	Responsibility and involvement
APRE (Coordinator) And UoY (Scientific Coordinator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validating the proposed exploitation, dissemination and communication strategy; Providing feedback and approval on the communication and dissemination contents to be released on behalf of SUPERSHINE (i.e., project website, leaflet, infopacks). Maximising the visibility of the results developed in the project. Ensuring that the project results have a clear orientation and fulfil market needs.
ICONS (WP6 leader)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leading and coordinating dissemination, communication and exploitation activities. Developing an integrated communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy to be implemented for the duration of the project. Developing the SUPERSHINE visual identity and various communication materials i.e. flyers, project video. Designing, and updating of the project website. Producing the content to be published on the project website and external channels, newsletters and social media platforms, together with the active contribution of all the partners. Monitoring the impact of communication materials produced and distributed for SUPERSHINE. Delivering regular updates of the communication plan based on the project's emerging dissemination and communication requirements. Supporting the mapping of KERs and the development of exploitation strategies for the post-project. Identifying and analysing stakeholders that may be target of dissemination and exploitation activities.
EEIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing and maintaining the SUPERSHINE website
All SUPERSHINE partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing inputs to create the SUPERSHINE website and other communication materials. Keeping ICONS informed as to relevant progress made by the project in their respective work packages. Boosting SUPERSHINE' presence on social media. Contributing to the definition of KERs, exploitation strategies and the stakeholder mapping. Providing ICONS with the list of events and publications they will be attending on behalf of SUPERSHINE. Mobilizing networks and connections for a wider outreach and promotion of SUPERSHINE.

Monitoring

ICONS's monitoring process

The impact of SUPERSHINE's DC products will be measured throughout the duration of the project. This will be done by monitoring and studying the project's ability to reach and engage with its target audiences.

Online media outreach will be calculated using a methodology that relies on automated tools that collect reliable statistics and data. The effectiveness of workshops and webinars will be measured based on the number of attendees and feedback to be collected at the end of each event.

Matomo will be used to assess the performance of the project website. It will be used extensively to retrieve available data about the traffic (in terms of the number of views, sessions, and users' behaviour) and the audience it reaches out to.

Press and news releases and journalistic articles will be monitored as well by calculating the outreach generated by the spontaneous take-ups of the SUPERSHINE content on websites and social media channels. This reporting activity will be done using Nuvi®, social media analytics programs i.e., Twitter Analytics, Facebook Insights and YouTube Analytics and data coming from external platforms and multipliers.

ICONS's engagement indexes: CEI encompassing - PEI, SEI, WEI

Outreach and engagement indicators are not sufficient to assess the evolution of the project acceptance level. The "outreach" provides an estimate of audience size, not its interest level. The "engagement" parameter describes the interest and overall impacts on a community but should be read in conjunction with the outreach to draw relevant conclusions on engagement. To this end, composite indicators are calculated for each area of activity: **Website Engagement Index (WEI)**, **Social media Engagement Index (SEI)** and the **Publication Engagement Index (PEI)**. They are computed as the ratio between the corresponding engagement and outreach indicators. This allows ICONS to analyse the DC impacts for each area of activity separately.

The **Community Engagement Index (CEI)**² developed by ICONS integrates all communication activities into one single metric. The total engagement (outreach) value is calculated by adding together the engagement (outreach) values calculated for the individual indicators.

The ratio between the engagement and outreach values collected for each single editorial product can be used for another analysis tool developed by ICONS, namely the impact quadrants as in Figure below. In the plot, the x and y axes report the publication outreach and engagement values respectively. Each editorial product is represented with a bubble whose radius is given by the ratio between the corresponding engagement and outreach values. The two axes cross at the average values across the editorial products in question. The bubble distribution allows us to see which news items have performed better in terms of outreach and engagement. This is a valuable tool for correcting and fine-tuning the SUPERSHINE communication and dissemination strategy. The plot is dynamic, as the coordinates of the bubble vary with time as more data is collected.

The CEI will measure the actual engagement of the SUPERSHINE community via the project contents delivered on the internet and the social media. It portrays the univocal relation between any project content

² Folco Giuliana, Gaboardi Elena, Lischetti Serena, Martinoli Mario, Mazzolo Giulio, & Schmid Elisabeth (2022). Two new tools for science communication assessment: the community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985584>

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

available on the web and social media and the actual interactions of online visitors coming across that content. The CEI is a function of the outreach and engagement values, with low values of the CEI indicating little relative interest by the target audience.

Figure 3 - Impact quadrant where each bubble corresponds to an editorial publication

The projects' visual identity

An appealing and consistent visual project identity is key to reaching out effectively to stakeholders, helping the project increase its influence and impact. The project logo has been developed starting from the SUPERSHINE brand personality exercise, which highlights the main features, characteristics, and elements the project partners want to convey when communicating about the project.

The brand identity draws inspiration from the SUPER-i logo, incorporating elements that resonate with its visual aesthetics. The logo symbolizes a fundamental concepts of the project: the district, while the SUPER-i logo represent the building.

The colours and typography that make up the project's visual identity and inform the web design were selected to remove any barrier to accessing it. This assures users do not feel excluded due to an impairment.

Figure 4 - SUPERSHINE logo - main version

D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1

All dissemination items and publications to be released by SUPERSHINE, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union research and innovation programme and display the European emblem.

Exploitation strategy

The SUPERSHINE Consortium adopts an impact-driven approach to boost the exploitation of project results, i.e., make concrete use of results for commercial, societal, and political purposes. In particular, the Consortium has envisioned preliminary exploitation pathways to stimulate broader replication of KERs and support the partners' capitalization of project results.

The consortium brings together complementary expertise from 20 partners from various countries to build the integrated SUPERSHINE package for social and affordable housing district demonstration deployment. These partners include local authorities and public bodies, university and research partners, industry and SMEs, and financial partners.

Therefore, the exploitation approach must provide a high degree of flexibility to account for the multiple type of partners and exploitation routes, while following a structured methodology. As anticipated in Table 1, Key exploitable results in SUPERSHINE consist of blueprint models and technologies, as well as knowledge and expertise gained in the project with a high potential for transferability and replicability, generating commercial and non-commercial opportunities for project partners. As such, the exploitation plan will detail all steps for the use and successful uptake of the SUPERSHINE results to maximize the project's impact. The exploitation strategies will draw on the following key pillars:

- Replication of project implementations towards fellow cities and upscaling in lighthouse districts.
- Sustainability plan of the SUPERSHINE Portal.
- Upscaling of technology TRLs and commercialization.
- Product/service development based on knowledge generated.
- Commercial exploitation of financial mechanisms and models.
- Academic and research exploitation.

These exploitation strategies will be better articulated during the project and will be completed by the end, thanks to further questionnaires, workshops, and direct interviews with the Consortium partners. A comprehensive mapping of key exploitable results is foreseen in D6.3 Library of Key Exploitable Results and Stakeholder Mapping. Individual and joint exploitation strategies will be described in D6.5 Final Exploitation Plan. The following exploitation pillars are anticipated by the Consortium:

Replication and upscaling

All KERs will be instrumental for the replication of solutions in the fellow cities already identified within the project but also extending these benefits to other cities beyond the project's boundaries. The active participation of partners such as ECG, INSME, Housing Europe association (HE), the Danish Association of Social Housing Organisations (BL), and public authorities (Ater Trieste and Riga) will also provide valuable support for upscaling efforts within the lighthouse districts (i.e. expanding implementations to a larger, more widespread, scale), while ensuring that the SUPERSHINE approach can be effectively replicated. Specifically, the insights and expertise gained from the lighthouse districts in Trieste, Riga, and FaellesBO will serve as best practices, providing guidance to fellow districts in assessing the social and financial models for an urban transformation project aimed at revitalizing social housing and mitigating energy poverty. The project will also contribute to the development of City Climate Contracts (CCC) by harmonising the different blueprint models for wide replication across the EU.

The exploitation plan will detail partners' intentions, roles and overall governance in supporting these replication strategies (towards fellow cities, and other interested parties outside the consortium boundaries), and upscaling plans (in the case of the lighthouses).

Sustainability plan of the SUPERSHINE portal

The SUPERSHINE portal will serve as a central reference point and hub for enterprises, stakeholders, and both institutional and private investors. Additionally, it will seamlessly integrate the "one-stop shop" concept, allowing existing market actors to offer their services through it. Ensuring the platform's sustainability beyond the project's conclusion is of utmost importance. The exploitation strategy for this result will encompass not only technical considerations but also governance, vision, and financial sustainability. In this regard, the consortium has already identified potential maintenance options, including:

- 1) Integrating it into a partner or stakeholder's online presence.
- 2) Maintaining the portal as it is and transferring operational responsibility to one or more partners or stakeholders.
- 3) Retaining specific parts of the portal, such as the e-Room, and integrating them into a partner or stakeholder's online presence.
- 4) Facilitating the transfer of data from the SUPERSHINE portal to another partner or stakeholder application.

Furthermore, two financial sustainability options are also under consideration:

- *Portal as-is with Free Access:* This option allows for unrestricted access to all non-confidential data collected during the project. This data can be easily replicated ("copied") to partner websites or even made available through DEEP (a non-commercial platform).
- *Portal PLUS:* This option involves offering an enhanced, paid service. It includes the addition of supplementary analytics layers and/or data sets, which will be managed by a project partner or potentially external entities. This commercial approach aims to provide added value to users willing to invest in more comprehensive and specialized services.

It is important to highlight that additional project outcomes, specifically KER1, KER2, KER3, and KER4 (see Table 1), serve as crucial sources of content for the SUPERSHINE portal. Consequently, the portal will play a pivotal role in facilitating the exploitation and adoption of these KERs. Moreover, it will support the replication of the SUPERSHINE approach, ensuring its wider implementation and impact.

Product/service development based on knowledge generated

Leveraging the knowledge generated within KERs 1, 2, 3, and 4, which pertain to business models, financing schemes, and the outcomes of the LCA analysis, SUPERSHINE partners have the opportunity to develop consulting and advisory services. These services can serve dual purposes. Firstly, they can harness the high replicability potential of SUPERSHINE, making it accessible to a broader audience. Secondly, they can facilitate its adoption by offering strategic guidance to market players who may lack the requisite expertise, particularly in local aspects.

Furthermore, the financial mechanisms and models outlined in KER1 present a valuable opportunity for commercial partners, such as TENDER, with a specific focus on finance. These partners are dedicated to incorporating innovative financial mechanisms and business models into their operations. This not only enables them to cater to their existing customers but also expands their customer base, further promoting the adoption of these innovative financial mechanisms and business models.

Upscaling of technology TRLs and commercialisation

SUPERSHINE will demonstrate a set of innovative technologies (KER4) within the lighthouse cities. These technologies will optimize resource utilization while simultaneously promoting well-being and sustainable lifestyles. Throughout the project, the selection of these technologies will be based on the specific needs and requirements of the lighthouse district residents. They will be seamlessly delivered through comprehensive renovation packages offered via the SUPERSHINE “One Stop Shop” (KER5), ensuring guaranteed energy savings for both social housing residents and managers.

This testing phase will serve as a proof-of-concept, demonstrating the feasibility, effectiveness, and efficiency of these innovative solutions. Consequently, a central objective of the exploitation strategy for the project’s technology partners will be to advance the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of energy-related renovation technologies in these specific use cases. Furthermore, technologies that are market-ready will undergo fine-tuning within the scope of the project. They may also benefit from the "One Stop Shop" channel as part of KER5, further facilitating their integration and adoption within the market.

Academic and research exploitation

With universities and research centres participating in the consortium, SUPERSHINE will create a number of Postdoc positions. The new knowledge generated will be integrated in university courses. Moreover, the new knowledge will be leveraged in further EU and national research projects. To this regard, research, and academic partners (UoY, CIRCE, CARTIF, APRE) anticipate scientific publication in peer reviewed journals addressing all KERs to share the findings with a larger audience of stakeholders. Furthermore, increased know-how on multi-stakeholder dialogue will feed APRE support services as NCPs, as well as training offer to the Italian R&I community and future projects.

The strategies outlined above will be discussed with all project partners and further detailed for all KERs identified. This collaborative effort will involve the active participation and expertise of all project partners, fostering a collective approach to strategy development, to ensure that each KER is addressed with a tailored and well-considered strategy, taking into account the unique challenges and opportunities associated.

Conclusions

This Plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication presents the overall PDEC of SUPERSHINE.

Partners can refer to this deliverable to align their local communication to that of the project, as it provides visual and content guidelines. Also, it provides an overview of the main tools and channels to be used for dissemination of project results, as well as the monitoring strategy that will be developed.

The channels and formats illustrated in this deliverable will ensure awareness, engagement and uptake by professional stakeholders and the general public. Their efficiency and outreach will be monitored periodically thereby allowing the project to understand and fine-tune its contents and the overall DEC strategy over time.

This document also contains the premise of the exploitation strategy, starting from the preliminary identification of KERs and stakeholder groups. Partners can find in this document the methodology that will be applied to define joint and individual exploitation strategies and the steps that will be carried out to ensure effective exploitation of project results.

This deliverable will be subject to future updates (M29) to fine-tune the post-project strategy and to provide recommendations for the implementation of future DEC strategies in other like-minded projects. A preliminary analysis on KERs, exploitation strategies and stakeholders will be presented in D6.3 (M14). The exploitation strategy will be then consolidated at the end of the project, providing a comprehensive view of exploitation strategies and target segments in the D6.5 Exploitation plan (M41).

References

Hesterberg, C., & Stiffler, M. O. (2015). EU 2020 and the Question of Social Housing: A Critical Assessment of European Union Policies Relating to Social Housing.

Scanlon, K., Whitehead, C., & Fernández Arrigoitia, M. (Eds.). (2014). Social Housing in Europe. Online ISBN: 9781118412367. DOI: 10.1002/9781118412367.

Pittini, A., Laino, E., & European Social Housing Observatory. (2011). Housing Europe Review 2012: The Nuts and Bolts of European Social Housing Systems. CECODHAS Housing Europe's Observatory.

European Parliament, Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union, Braga, M., Palvarini, P., Social housing in the European Union, Publications Office, 2013, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2861/29935>

Rohrer, L., & Lidmo, J. (2022). Combating Energy Poverty in Social Housing: Interregional Dialogues on the Impact of COVID-19. Social Green - Regional policies towards greening the housing sector: Fifth-call activities final report. Nordregio. September 2022.

UN-HABITAT. (2009). Financing Affordable Social Housing in Europe (The Human Settlements Financing Tools and Best Practices Series). Nairobi, Kenya: United Nations Human Settlements Programme.